

Investigation of palladium- cobalt alloy nanoparticles embedded in nitrogen-rich graphite composite as a high volumetric capacity compact hydrogen storage material.

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Abstract:

As a promising storage medium, the hydrogen-storage properties of carbon composites have been explored over the past few decades. Most of these materials will have high gravimetric storage capacity but low volumetric capacity due to their high specific surface area. For a practical storage device, both VD and GD are important, since the device must be efficient and compact. In this context, the hydrogen storage properties of a novel graphite-based composite, Pd₃Co/N-Gr, are explored in this work, which shows a maximum gravimetric storage capacity of 6.5 ± 0.1 wt % and a volumetric capacity of 143.0 g/L at 3 MPa and room temperature. Moreover, through a very simple one- step synthesis procedure, the efficient decoration of the alloy catalyst nanoparticles as well as the incorporation of nitrogen is done over the graphite layers.

Key words: hydrogen storage, palladium cobalt alloy nano particles, spillover mechanism, catalyst nanoparticles, volumetric capacity, graphite.

1. Introduction

Since hydrogen has emerged as the most desirable alternative energy source, several methods for its storage have become significant over the last few decades. The attempts to make an ideal hydrogen storage material are still under research. The efficiency of a hydrogen storage material is typically measured by two parameters- gravimetric density (GD) and volumetric density (VD). GD means the weight percentage of hydrogen stored in the total weight of the system, and VD is the measurement of the stored hydrogen mass per unit volume of the system. The volumetric capacity can be derived from the gravimetric capacity if the bulk density is known. For practical applications, both parameters are important because a hydrogen storage device must be light and compact ¹⁻⁵.

Carbon nanomaterials have been identified as promising storage media for hydrogen, since they possess auspicious qualities such as high specific surface area, low density, tunable pore distribution, fast kinetics, stability, and large-scale production. However, the new trend, two-dimensional material graphene, is predicted to be a good material for hydrogen storage. As a quasi-two-dimensional system, the volume density is not well defined for pristine single-layered graphene. Hydrogen can be adsorbed on carbon materials in two main ways – physical adsorption and chemisorption. Calculations based on post-Hartree-Fock/empirical potentials and quantum treatments of hydrogen have shown that both GD and VD are improved in a multi-layered graphene system compared to a single-layered system. From these studies, the highest values of GD and VD are obtained for an inter-layer separation of ~6-8 Å. Therefore, these studies point out that for hydrogen storage devices, multi-layered graphene is more suitable than single-layer. In graphene multi-layers, the attractive Van der Waals forces of two combined layers will introduce a ‘nano pump effect’. Thus, the internal pressure between the layers will again increase, reaching a high level of compression ⁶⁻⁹.

The practical reach of multi-layered graphene is mainly based on the graphene-derived nanostructures such as graphene oxides and reduced graphene oxides, graphene nano ribbons, graphite nano platelets,

graphene nano fibres, multi-walled carbon nanotubes, etc. or porous carbons which are generally manufactured as powders; and the drawback of the powdered medium is the limited packing density. One of the reported easy methods to get these graphene-derived multilayers is based on the exfoliation of graphene oxide (GO) and its chemical functionalization¹⁰⁻¹³. The GO-exfoliated graphene sheets had a capacity (GD) of 0.68 wt%, and their chemical modification with nitrogen and palladium improved the capacity (GD) to 4.3 wt%¹⁴⁻¹⁶. However, in these works, the VD is very poor, as they possess comparatively large surface-area graphene-like sheets. Moreover, the synthesis method for these graphene sheets and the chemical modifications are multi-step processes that involve an intermediate product, GO. Thus, the cost of production is high, and the yield from the parental product, graphite, is low. In this scenario, we introduce the highly hydrogen-affinitive catalyst sites directly into the graphite layers, thereby dissociating hydrogen molecules locally at these sites, followed by further adsorption of hydrogen atoms by the layers, which will improve the volumetric capacity (VD) as well as the ease of production. It is well established that when nitrogen is combined with carbon, it can provide a much higher hydrogen adsorption capacity than pure carbon¹⁷. Again, for introducing hydrogen spill-over catalyst sites, the noble metal palladium is the most favourable option. However, its high cost and corrosion in hydrogen environments will push it away from the hydrogen economy. Thus, by alloying cost-effective metals, such as cobalt, one can address both cost and corrosion issues. Hence, in the present work, attempts are being made to improve the hydrogen storage capacity of pure graphite by introducing nitrogen sites and decorating it with palladium-cobalt alloy catalyst nanoparticles¹⁸. Efforts have been made to reduce synthesis complexity through a single-step catalytic chemical vapour deposition process, which can effectively produce palladium-cobalt alloy catalyst nanoparticles embedded in nitrogen-rich graphite. For effective alloying of Co with noble metals such as Pd or Pt, the 3:1 ratio is preferable, since it can provide the proper geometric features, the highest atomic ordering, and the highest electron density¹⁹⁻²⁷. Hence, the present work discusses the synthesis and hydrogen storage properties of palladium-cobalt alloy catalyst nanoparticles decorated with nitrogen-rich graphite (Pd₃Co/N-Gr).

2. Experimental section:

2.1. Materials used:

Graphite powder (<45 μm size), melamine powder, palladium (II) chloride (99%), cobaltous chloride hexahydrate ($\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) (all from Sigma Aldrich), high-purity hydrogen gas(99.99%) and deionised water.

2.2. Synthesis:

Synthesis of Pd₃Co-N-Gr involves a simple, single-step process.

The as purchased graphite powders were mixed with melamine in (1:1) ratio using sufficient amount of DI water by a mechanical stirring of 15 minutes; following which the required amount of metal precursors (1 wt% standard solutions of PdCl₂ and CoCl₂ · 6H₂O to satisfy the 20 wt% of the targeted loading of Pd and Co in 3:1 ratio) were added and continued the stirring for 6 hours and finally the mixture was dried overnight in a vacuum oven at 60°C.

The dried mixture is well ground and uniformly loaded into a quartz boat placed in the centre of a tubular furnace, flushed with Argon gas for 10 minutes, and then the heat treatment is started. As the sample temperature reaches 250 °C, hydrogen gas is introduced into the system for 30 minutes. Then the system temperature is raised to 700 °C and held for 30 more minutes. The furnace was then cooled to room temperature, and the product was carefully removed and labelled as Pd₃Co-N-Gr.

2.3. Material characterisations:

The basic signature of the sample is explored using powder X-ray diffraction pattern (PANalytical Xpert Pro X-ray Diffractometer). The morphology as well as elemental composition is analysed using a field emission scanning electron microscope [FESEM, FEI QUANTA 400F) with energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) analysis and a transmission electron microscope (TEM, FEITecnaiG²20 S-TWIN, 200 keV). The Micromeritics ASAP2020 analyser was used to observe the BET surface area and pore size distribution.

2.4. Hydrogen interaction studies:

A high-pressure Sievert's apparatus is used to investigate the hydrogen adsorption/desorption properties of the Pd₃Co- N- Gr sample using the pressure reduction method; the schematic of which is shown in Figure 6. The calibrated unit is loaded with the sample, and a degassing process at 300 °C under high vacuum is done for 2 hours to remove the moisture and other dissolved impurities. Following two trial activation cycles to empower the gas-adsorbing sites, actual measurement cycles were carried out. Each cycle has activated the sample at 300 °C for 2 hours and cooled down to 100 °C under high vacuum (10⁻⁶ Torr). Now, high-purity hydrogen gas is allowed to react with the activated sample until saturation is reached. Again, the sample temperature was reduced to 500 C, then to room temperature, and the equilibrium pressure was recorded at each temperature. The pressure-composition isotherms were plotted using hydrogen storage weight percentages calculated at different pressure drops.

The kinetic studies were performed at 100 °C, 2.4 MPa pressure. After activating the sample at 300 °C for 2 hours, the temperature is reduced to 100 °C, and the sample is suddenly exposed to 2.4 MPa of hydrogen. The progress of pressure reduction was noted down using a stop clock. During the entire experiment, the room temperature was maintained at 25 ± 10 °C.

3. Results and discussion:

Through an easy and convenient single-step synthesis process, the 'as purchased' graphite sheets were transformed into nitrogen-rich, alloy catalyst nano particles embedded (Pd₃Co/N- Gr) hydrogen storage media. The 'as purchased' graphite powder consists of two-dimensional sliding sheets. The proposed synthesis procedure should favour two processes: the decomposition of melamine into nitrogen groups, followed by their subsequent doping within the layers of graphite, and the reduction of Pd and Co from their respective precursors, with subsequent nucleation as alloy nanoparticles on the nitrogen-rich graphite substrate. When the well-mixed graphite powder with precursors was exposed to a systematic heating procedure in a tubular furnace in the presence of hydrogen and argon, the desired composition of nitrogen, palladium and cobalt was assimilated in the graphite matrix. As the temperature exceeded 2800 °C, the melamine began decomposing into nitrogen functional groups, which could subsequently be incorporated into the SP₂ networks of the graphite sheets. When hydrogen gas was allowed into the

system, Pd and Co were released from their corresponding precursors. Again, when the temperature is raised to 700°C, the Pd and Co were deposited in the nitrogen-rich sites of graphite layers as nanoparticle clusters. Thus, the nitrogen sites will favour the nucleation of catalyst nanoparticles. To investigate the role of nitrogen on hydrogen adsorption, we have synthesised a nitrogen-free sample (melamine), i.e., palladium-cobalt alloy catalyst nanoparticle-decorated graphite (Pd₃Co/Gr), and compared its hydrogen storage performance. A schematic showing the alloy catalyst distribution over the graphite layers is shown in Figure 1. This method successfully immobilises palladium-cobalt alloy catalyst nanoparticles in a 3:1 ratio on a nitrogen-rich graphite substrate. Here we have adopted the optimized value of 20-wt% for catalyst loading. Each grain of the graphite can permit the decoration of the nanoparticles on the top and bottom layers as well as the edges of the middle layers. In figure 1, the cyan coloured balls represent the carbon atoms and the pink balls represent the Pd₃Co nano particles. The inset images (round) are the TEM images of graphite and Pd₃Co/N- Gr.

The normalized powder XRD patterns of graphite and Pd₃Co- N- Gr is as shown in figure 2. The graphite hexagonal planes are revealed through (002) and (004) peaks. In Pd₃Co- N- Gr specimen, the palladium face centred cubic (fcc) crystalline lattice is exhibited through the signature peaks of Pd (111), (200), (220), (311) and (222) planes along with the graphitic (002) and (004) peaks. Here the Pd (111) peak is broader and shorter, indicating the nano phase of palladium. In addition, there are no reflections corresponding to the elemental cobalt; since the catalyst contains single face fcc disordered structure (solid solution) which is an indication of the perfect alloying of Co in Pd lattice. These results clearly suggest the successful immobilization of palladium cobalt alloy nano particle over the graphite substrate. Moreover, the nitrogen rich graphite substrate is well appreciated to accommodate the catalyst nano phase in its binary alloy form without any structural modification. This is a good indication of projected catalytic activity towards hydrogen as estimated²⁸⁻³⁰. The average particle size is extracted as ~ 20 nm for Pd₃Co nanoparticle from the full width half maximum of Pd (111) peak using Debye Scherer formula; which is in agreement with the observed microscopic images.

Again, the elemental composition and distribution of the sample are analysed using elemental mapping and energy dispersive X- ray analysis. The EDX spectra (see figure S₁ of ESI[†]) shows the composition

of elements in the Pd₃Co- N- Gr sample. The extracted wt% for each element is as follows- C (61.30 %), N (19.02 %), Pd (14.75 %) and Co (4.93 %). From this data, it can be concluded that the sample contains the proposed ~ 20-wt % of Pd and Co together in a 3:1 ratio.

The surface morphology of the sample is revealed through the microscopic images shown figure 3. The TEM and SEM images of graphite layers in the as purchased powdered sample is shown in figures 3 (a) and 3 (c) respectively. When treated through the catalytic chemical vapour deposition synthesis procedure as explained previously, the pristine graphite layers became enriched with nitrogen as well as embedded with the catalyst nano particles. The SEM and TEM images in figures 3 (b) and 3 (d) show the random distribution of the nanoparticles in the layers. From the figure 3 (e) and (f), the size of the embedded nano particles are estimated as ~ 20 nm which in agreement with the XRD pattern calculations. In order to confirm spatial distribution of elements in the sample, the elemental mapping of the images is done. The representative elemental mapping of the sample is as shown in figure 4. It is quite evident from the figure that Pd and Co nanoparticles are distributed randomly over the nitrogen rich graphite layers.

The gas adsorbing sites of the synthesized sample were analysed through the BET surface area and porosity measurements. The data are recorded using the nitrogen adsorption- desorption isotherms at 77K as shown in figure 5 (a). The observed BET surface area of the Pd₃Co- N- Gr sample is 0.5939 m²/g; while for pure graphite it is 1.2021 m²/g. The BJH pore size distribution is also exhibited in figure 5 (b). The isotherms are observed to be of type IV with a hysteresis in the range of (0.45 -0.99) P/P₀; according to Bruner-Deming-Deming-Teller classification, which is the characteristic of a meso- porous material. The pore size distribution shows a range of pores between (2-120) nm with a maximum volume at (2- 50) nm which is meso-porous. These qualities make the present material as a good gas adsorbing media. It is observed that the specific surface area of graphite is decreased after the decoration of catalyst nanoparticle. This can be attributed to the sealing of some pore by the catalyst nanoparticles. Moreover, some sites, including the catalyst centers will be not approachable for nitrogen adsorption; can be active in hydrogen adsorption. Therefore, in practical, for hydrogen adsorption the surface area will be higher ³⁰⁻³².

3.1. Hydrogen adsorption studies:

As mentioned earlier, the hydrogen adsorption -desorption studies were performed in Sieverts apparatus (see figure 6) using pressure reduction method by applying the Van der Waals corrections for the hydrogen gas. Consider the three conditions of the system, where an initial pressure P_i occupies the initial volume V_i with the number of moles n_i , an equilibrium pressure P_{eq} at the initial volume V_i with the number of moles n_1 and an equilibrium pressure P_{eq} at the cell volume V_c with the number of moles n_2 . Applying the Van der Waals correction coefficients 'a' and 'b' for hydrogen, these three conditions will be evolved as the following gas equations.

$$abn_i^3 + aV_i n_i^2 + (RT + P_i b)V_i^2 n_i - P_i V_i^3 = 0$$

$$abn_1^3 + aV_i n_1^2 + (RT + P_{eq} b)V_i^2 n_1 - P_{eq} V_i^3 = 0$$

$$abn_2^3 + aV_c n_2^2 + (RT + P_{eq} b)V_c^2 n_2 - P_{eq} V_c^3 = 0$$

where T is the sample cell temperature and R is the universal gas constant.

The number of moles of hydrogen adsorbed can be calculated as follows:

$$\Delta n = n_i - (n_1 + n_2)$$

By knowing the value of Δn , the hydrogen concentration of the sample (wt %) for a given mass 'm' at an equilibrium pressure P_{eq} (gravimetric capacity) can be calculated as

$$Wt\% \text{ of } (H) = 2 \Delta n / m$$

Thus, it shows the mass of hydrogen in 100 grams of the stored material. By knowing the value of the bulk density (ρ) of the material, we can find the volumetric capacity, i.e.; the amount of hydrogen present in the unit volume of the stored material as gram per litre (g/L).

The pressure - composition (P-C) isotherms of Pd₃Co- N- Gr were plotted for different temperatures as shown in figure 7(a). The isotherms were recorded in a temperature range of 25 – 100°C with a pressure range of (0.1 – 3) MPa. As the sample temperature is increased, the storage capacity is also increased

as expected; since gas molecules will get enough kinetic energy to escape the barrier potentials. The desorption studies at room temperature show the high reversibility of the adsorption process. Here for comparison and study the role of nitrogen in the adsorption process, the P-C isotherms of the Pd₃Co – Gr specimen in figure 7(b) is also considered.

From the isotherm study of Pd₃Co- N- Gr sample, at 2 MPa pressure and room temperature, the storage capacity is estimated as 5.1 ± 0.1 wt% hydrogen. Comparing to the high surface area carbon materials like graphene, activated carbon, MOFs or chemically modified carbon materials, this capacity is quite high. For pure graphite or few layer graphene, the reported value is less than 1 wt % under the same conditions. For Pd₃Co- Gr sample at 2 MPa and room temperature, the capacity is 2.9 ± 0.1 wt%. A maximum storage capacity of 6.5 ± 0.1 wt% at 3 MPa pressure is observed in Pd₃Co- N- Gr specimen while it is 3.6 ± 0.1 wt% for Pd₃Co- Gr. These results support Pd₃Co- N- Gr as a potential gravimetric capacity material.

For calculating the volumetric capacity, the bulk density of graphite is taken as 2.2 (g/cc). Converting the gravimetric capacity to volumetric density, we can get a maximum capacity of 143 g/L at 3MPa pressure and room temperature. Comparing with the other reported high capacity carbon materials, the present material is having very high volumetric capacity. For the pristine single layer graphene, the main practical difficulty in making hydrogen storage device is that its volumetric density cannot be defined; being a quasi-2 dimensional system. The other graphene derived materials such as reduced graphene oxides, nano tubes and activated carbons, carbon nitrides, etc., and their Pd modified forms are also facing the low volumetric capacity due to their high specific surface area. Table 1 (ESI[†]) contains the comparative study of the various reported carbon based materials and their Pd modified forms in the view of GD and VD. Figure 8 shows the variation of volumetric capacity with surface area for different carbon composites based on the reported data ⁸. Here the present material Pd₃Co- N- Gr shows the highest volumetric capacity with considerable gravimetric density. Thus, this material is suitable for the fabrication of compact hydrogen storage devices.

Generally, the interaction between graphite and hydrogen is of interest in three important research areas: molecular hydrogen formation in space, hydrogen storage and hydrogen- wall interactions in fusion reactors. The permeation of hydrogen through graphite is described as molecular flow. The chemisorbed hydrogen in the graphite can combine to form H₂ molecule before desorption. Once the spill over will start, the atomic hydrogen will migrate from the catalyst site to the layers. The rate of diffusion is temperature dependant. The adsorbed hydrogen atom can form dimers. Here in this case, the nitrogen sites in the sample will contribute to the accumulation of H atoms. In the spill over process, a flux of hydrogen atoms will be released from the catalyst site due to the dissociative chemisorption of molecular hydrogen due to the interaction between Pd₃Co nano particles, first flows into the material in the vicinity of catalyst site like 'a bridge' and then continue to flow through the substrate. The unsaturated bonds resulting from SP² carbon are responsible for H adsorption and subsequent diffusion. The temperature -programmed desorption (TPD) and density functional theory (DFT) studies have pointed out the temperature dependence of diffusion coefficients through Arrhenius equations $D = D_0 \exp(-E_a/k_B T)$. As temperature increases, the diffusion coefficient will increase. At lower temperature, the quantum effect will be dominating. In fact, molecular hydrogen is expected to diffuse faster in graphite layers than atomic hydrogen. It is found that diffusion coefficient is larger for H₂ than H. Typically, at 300 K, $D = 6.9 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$ for H₂ and $D = 9.2 \times 10^{-10} \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$ for H. Thus, when the hydrogen atoms will diffuse through the void space, they will come closer than a minimum distance and recombine. As time progresses, the adsorbed H atom will migrate from layer to layer as H₂ molecules. In short, the first H atom chemisorbed in the surface behaves as a surface defect for the subsequent adsorption of the second H atom. Thus, the trapping- detrapping mechanism continues³³⁻³⁹.

By calculation, it is clear that chemical modification has improved the capacity of pure graphite by more than 350%. Figure S₂ of ESI[†] shows the kinetic behaviour of Pd₃Co- N- Gr towards hydrogen. As soon as the sample is exposed to hydrogen, the reaction is happening exponentially and reaches a saturation level. All these performance can be attributed to the catalytic activity of Pd₃Co nanoparticles and their synergetic interaction with the nitrogen rich graphite. The alloy nano particle decoration has not only improved the capacity of the material, but also contributed to the stability of the material. The

alloying of Co with Pd could reduce the hydrogen corrosion in Pd, which could retain the capacity of the material after several numbers of cycles (see figure S₃ in ESI[†]). The catalytic performance of the Pd₃Co nanoparticles in the nitrogen rich graphite can be modelled using the hydrogen spill over mechanism. Figure 9 shows the schematics of the reaction mechanism.

The catalyst centres will attract incoming H₂ molecules, split them into H atoms, and pump them to the graphite layers via subsequent diffusion. Thus, the graphite layers can hold the H atoms. Once the mechanism is started, the catalyst centres will appear as a virtual source of hydrogen atoms to the underlying nitrogen-rich graphite matrix. Comparing the performance of both Pd₃Co- N- Gr and Pd₃Co- Gr, we can infer the role of nitrogen in the catalytic activity of the material. The nitrogen sites could improve catalyst nanoparticle decoration during synthesis. Here, it is estimated that almost 160% of the stored hydrogen is associated with nitrogen sites. During the hydrogen reaction, nitrogen sites can enhance the physisorption of H₂ molecules within the graphite layers. Moreover, the nitrogen sites will accumulate the diffused H atoms as clusters in the graphite layers. Both physisorbed and chemisorbed hydrogen will be packed between the layers of graphite, which will be responsible for its highly improved GD and VD.

4. Conclusion:

A potential high volumetric as well as gravimetric capacity hydrogen storage material is developed through a simple one-step synthesis process. The material is found to have the highest volumetric capacity compared to the other carbon-based composites under similar conditions. The synthesis process is scalable and cost-effective because it modifies the raw material, graphite, in a single step. The alloy catalyst mechanism and role of nitrogen in the hydrogen storage capacity of graphite are explored. The present material Pd₃Co- N- Gr could achieve a maximum gravimetric storage capacity of 6.5 ± 0.1 wt% and a volumetric capacity of 143.0 g/L under 3 MPa pressure and room temperature.

5. Supporting Information:

Electronic supplementary information (ESI[†]) includes EDX spectra, hydrogen sorption kinetics, a stability curve, and a table comparing the different materials.

6. Acknowledgement:

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7. Preprint statement:

This is a preprint version (v1, February 2026) of work extracted from the corresponding author's PhD thesis at IIT Madras. This manuscript was previously submitted to *Advanced Materials* and the *Journal of Physical Chemistry* (rejected), and may be submitted to peer-reviewed journals in the future.

Uploaded by the corresponding author for open dissemination and timestamping.

8. Data Availability and Statement:

This manuscript contains experimental results, simulations and theoretical analyses developed as a part of the PhD thesis at IIT Madras. No confidential or proprietary data is disclosed. Full methodology and context are documented in the publicly available IIT Madras PhD thesis repository. Supporting data is available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

9. Conflicts of Interest:

The authors declare no conflicts of interest. This work represents independent PhD research contributions developed under supervision at IIT Madras and is archived by the lead and corresponding author.

10. Author contributions:

Asalatha Nair*: Conceptualisation, methodology, data acquisition, formal analysis, investigation, original draft preparation, visualisation, project administration, corresponding author.

Sangeetha V: data acquisition help

Abhinaya S: data acquisition help

Sundara Ramaprabu: Supervision and validation.

11. Reference:

- (1) K. Spyrou, D. Gournis and P. Rudolf, *ECS J. Solid State Sci. Technol.*, 2013, **2**, M3160–M3169.
- (2) E. Masika and R. Mokaya, *Energy Environ. Sci.*, 2014, **9**, 427–434.
- (3) J. P. Singer, A. Mayergoyz, C. Portet, E. Schneider, Y. Gogotsi and J. E. Fischer, *Microporous Mesoporous Mater.*, 2008, **116**, 469–472.
- (4) Weidenthaler, Claudia and Felderhoff, Michael, *Energy Environ. Sci.*, 2011, **4**, 2495-2502.
- (5) J. Yang, A. Sudik, C. Wolverton and D. J. Siegel, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2010, **39**, 656–675.
- (6) S. Patchkovskii, J. S. Tse, S. N. Yurchenko, L. Zhechkov, T. Heine and G. Seifert, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.*, 2005, **102**, 10439–44.
- (7) K. Spyrou, D. Gournis and P. Rudolf, *ECS J. Solid State Sci. Technol.*, 2013, **2**, M3160–M3169.
- (8) V. Tozzini and V. Pellegrini, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, 2013, **15**, 80–9.
- (9) F. Bonaccorso, L. Colombo, G. Yu, M. Stoller, V. Tozzini, a C. Ferrari, R. S. Ruoff and V. Pellegrini, *Science (80-.)*, 2015, **347**, 1246501.
- (10) W. C. Xu, K. Takahashi, Y. Matsuo, Y. Hattori, M. Kumagai, S. Ishiyama, K. Kaneko and S. Iijima, *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy*, 2007, **32**, 2504–2512.
- (11) C. Pohlmann, L. Röntzsch, F. Heubner, T. Weißgärber and B. Kieback, *J. Power Sources*, 2013, **231**, 97–105.
- (12) Sevilla, Marta and Mokaya, Robert, *Energy Environ. Sci.*, 2014, **7**, 1250-1280.
- (13) C. Dillon and M. J. Heben, *Appl. Phys. A Mater. Sci. Process.*, 2001, **72**, 133–142.
- (14) G. Srinivas, Y. Zhu, R. Piner, N. Skipper, M. Ellerby and R. Ruoff, *Carbon N. Y.*, 2010, **48**, 630–635.
- (15) B. P. Vinayan, R. Nagar and S. Ramaprabhu, *J. Mater. Chem. A*, 2013, **1**, 11192
- (16) S. K. Konda and A. Chen, *Materials Today*, 2016, **19**, 100- 108.
- (17) A. a. S. Nair, R. Sundara and N. Anitha, *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy*, 2015, **40**, 3259–3267.
- (18) A. A. S. Nair and S. Ramaprabhu, *J. Phys. Chem. C*, 2016, **120**, 9612- 9618.
- (19) Zhong, Z. Y.; Xiong, Z. T.; Sun, L. F.; Luo, J. Z.; Chen, P.; Wu, X.; Lin, J.; Tan, K. L. *Journal of Physical Chemistry B* **2002**, 9507–9513.
- (20) Squires, R. G. *Journal of Catalysis* **2 1963**, 338, 324–338.
- (21) Villarroel, M.; Baeza, P.; Escalona, N.; Ojeda, J.; Delmon, B.; Gil, J. M D *Applied Catalysis A General* **2008**, 345-347.
- (22) Manogaran, D.; Hwang, G. S. *Physical chemistry chemical physics : PCCP* **2013**, *15*, 12118–12123.
- (23) Oishi, K. *PhD Thesis, Universite de Montreal* **2012**.
- (24) Tahir, M.; Cao, C.; Butt, F. K.; Idrees, F.; Mahmood, N.; Ali, Z.; Aslam, I.; Tanveer, M.; Rizwan, M.; Mahmood, T. *Journal of Materials Chemistry A* **2013**, *1*, 13949.
- (25) Tahir, M.; Cao, C.; Butt, F. K.; Butt, S.; Idrees, F.; Ali, Z.; Aslam, I.; Tanveer, M.; Mahmood, A.; Mahmood, N. *CrystEngComm* **2014**, *16*, 1825.
- (26) Kaszkur, Z. , *Synchrotron Radiation in Natural Science* **2012**, *11*, 23.
- (27) J. Li, B. Shen, Z. Hong, B. Lin, B. Gao, Y. Chen, *Chemical Communications (Cambridge, England)* **48** (2012) 12017–9.
- (28) Obregón, S.; Colón, G. *Journal of Photochemistry and Photobiology A* : **2013**, *253*, 16–21.
- (29) Konda, S. K.; Chen, A. *Materials Today* **2015**, *00*, 2–10.

- (30) Adams, B. D.; Chen, A. *Materials Today* **2011**, *14*, 282–289.
- (31) Beaumont, S. K.; Alayoglu, S.; Specht, C.; Kruse, N.; Somorjai, G. *Nano Letters* **2014**, *14*, 4792–4796.
- (32) Huesges, B. Z.; Christmann, K. *Physical Chemistry*. **2013**, No. 0001, 0381.
- (33) M. Bonfanti, R. Martinazzo, G. F. Tantardini and A. Ponti, *J. Phys. Chem. C*, 2007, **111**, 5825–5829.
- (34) F. Marinelli and A. Allouche, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 2003, **368**, 609–615.
- (35) N. Rougeau, D. Teillet-Billy and V. Sidis, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 2006, **431**, 135–138.
- (36) L. Hornekær, Ž. Šljivančanin, W. Xu, R. Otero, E. Rauls, I. Stensgaard, E. Lægsgaard, B. Hammer and F. Besenbacher, *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 2006, **96**, 1–4.
- (37) Carlos P Herrero, Rafael Ramirez. *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics*, IOP Publishing, 2010, 43 (25), pp.255402. <10.1088/0022-3727/43/25/255402>.
- (38) M. Warrier, R. Schneider, E. Salonen and K. Nordlund, *Nucl. Fusion*, 2007, **47**, 1656–1663.
- (39) L. Chen, A. C. Cooper, G. P. Pez and H. Cheng, *Society*, 2007, 18995–19000.

12. Figures:

Figure 1- Structural schematics of as purchased graphite and Pd₃Co/N- Gr

Figure 2- Normalized XRD patterns of a) Pd₃Co/N- Gr and b) graphite

Figure 3- SEM images of (a) As purchased graphite (b) Pd₃Co/N- Gr and TEM images of (c) As purchased graphite (d) Pd₃Co/N- Gr

Figure 3- (e) and (f) – SEM/TEM images showing the Pd₃Co nanoparticle distribution

Figure 4- the representative elemental mapping of the Pd₃Co/N- Gr sample.

Figure 5 (a) - BET surface area analysis of samples – graphite and Pd₃Co/N- Gr
 -The nitrogen adsorption- desorption isotherms

Figure 5 (b) - Porosity analysis of graphite and Pd₃Co/N- Gr samples

Figure 6- the schematics of the Sieverts' apparatus used for hydrogen adsorption/desorption studies.

Figure 7 (a) - Hydrogen pressure – composition isotherms of Pd₃Co/N-Gr

Figure 7 (b) - Hydrogen pressure – composition isotherms of Pd₃Co/Gr

Figure 8- the variation of volumetric capacity with surface area for different carbon based composites based on the reported data (see Table -1 of ESI[†]).

Figure 9- Schematic representing the hydrogen adsorption mechanism in Pd₃Co/ N-Gr Structure